

Linking Research & Innovation for Gender Equality

D6.4 Dissemination and communication activities v3

WP6 - Dissemination and Communication

Version: 1.00

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Executive Summary

The CALIPER project drives structural change by implementing Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) in 7 Research Performing (UZG - FER, MTF - STU BA, ULB, ECE - NTUA, IRB, YU, UNILE) and 2 Research Funding (SRNSFG, UEFISDI) organisations. The project goal is to make research organisations more gender equal by increasing the number of female researchers in STEM, improving their career prospects, and integrating the gender dimension in research. A core aim is to involve management at senior and middle levels at an early stage of the project.

The project's dissemination and communication activities constitute a pivotal aspect of its overall design, given their role in promoting CALIPER's contributions toward gender equality. The project has adopted a multifaceted and detailed dissemination plan implemented via a set of concrete actions from the very beginning in order to:

- Raise awareness about the CALIPER project
- Increase engagement and encourage the involvement of the target groups in the project activities.
- Promote sustainability actions and best practices of CALIPER actions after the project's completion.

The current report constitutes the third, and final, report that aggregates the dissemination and communication efforts of the CALIPER Consortium, both as a whole and at partners level, to meet the above-listed goals. In the following pages, documentation of the project's activities is provided, covering the last reporting period, that is from M31 – July 2022 to M48 – December 2023. The deliverable includes:

- Updates on the project's branding and communication materials
- Descriptions and data about the project website and the social media channels
- Reporting of project's events, partners' events as well as synergies with other sister EU-funded projects of the broad network of GE projects and initiatives
- List of latest relevant project publications
- Links to project media, such as videos, news posts, newsletters and press releases prepared by the project and by project partners

What is more, the deliverable concludes with a summary of the project's efforts in relation to the corresponding dissemination and communication KPIs; and provides a concrete action plan for the project's exit strategy in what regards the dissemination of the project's completion and the establishment of a repository of CALIPER resources and outputs.

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Full form
CU	Cardiff University
GEPs	Gender Equality Plans
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
RPOs	Research Performing Organisations
RFOs	Research Funding Organisations
UZG - FER	University of Zagreb - Faculty of Electrical and Computer Engineering

MTF STU BA	Faculty of Materials Science and Technology - Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava
ULB	Université Libre de Bruxelles
ECE - NTUA	School of Electrical & Computer engineering - National Technical University of Athens
IRB	Institute for Research in Biomedicine in Barcelona
YU	Yasar University
UNILE	Salento University
SRNSFG	Shota Rustaveli National Science Foundation of Georgia
UEFISCDI	Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development & Innovation Funding in Romania
YAE	Young Academy of Europe

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose & Scope

The present deliverable is the third and final report of the activities implemented by the project partners to disseminate and communicate CALIPER. In particular, it presents the progress and results of the CALIPER dissemination and communication strategy for the period M31 – July 2022 to M48 – December 2023.

1.2 Target Audience

This report has both internal and external target audiences. It is aimed at all project partners to further develop/implement their individual and collaborative activities, as well as to identify needs and re-adjust the communication, dissemination and exploitation strategy. In addition, the document can be used as a guide and practical tool for “Horizon2020” – “Horizon Europe” dissemination managers of on-going and future projects, who may be willing to explore the CALIPER strategy and capitalise on it, as well as a guide/control point for the reviewers of the European Commission. Lastly, the current deliverable can be used by anyone who wishes to replicate the CALIPER dissemination approach.

1.3 Structure of the deliverable

The deliverable is structured into the following sections:

Chapter 1 introduces the document's target audience, the relationship to the other work packages and the structure.

Chapter 2 gives the overview of the reported activities implemented throughout the addressed period.

Chapter 3 provides a summative table of the documented information in relation to the project's KPIs

Chapter 4 completes the report with a conclusion that comments on the overall actions and proposes a list of key actions to be taken into account as the project's exit strategy.

The Annex section includes the CALIPER RPOs/RFOs key results posters created for the Joint Final Conference of the project.

1.4 Relation to other WPs & Tasks

The activities presented in this deliverable draw from and feed back into the overall actions of the project. In addition, this deliverable is closely interlinked with ‘WP5 - Engagement, change management and sustainability’ by sharing mutual objectives in terms of stakeholders’ engagement.

2 Reporting overview

This chapter entails the main documentation of CALIPER's dissemination and communication efforts within the covered period from M31 – July 2022 to M48 – December 2023. The reporting is provided in specific categories to facilitate an effective and appropriate presentation of CALIPER's activities. The sub-sections below address the project's branding latest updates, the online channels (project website and social media), the aggregate of the project's networking activities (project events, partners' events and synergies), the project's publication outputs and the media content drafted to promote CALIPER.

2.1 Project branding

During the reporting period addressed within this deliverable, the dissemination and communication activities of the project required the creation of updated communication materials to be used for the purposes of CALIPER branding. The latest materials were inspired by the CALIPER's logo colour pattern as well as the initial materials. Hence, the project showcased a high-quality level of branding, which was also versatile as it has been used in multiple occasions described below.

2.1.1 Leaflets and flyers

The new leaflet of the project was drafted to highlight the major outcomes from the first 12-month iteration of partners' GEPs and their relevant supporting co-design and implementation actions.

Figure 1. CALIPER new leaflet

The leaflet was created to promote CALIPER's impact in the context of [sister-project, RESISTIRÉ, final conference](#), and it was handed as a flyer to the physical attendees of the conference.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

Figure 2. CALIPER new leaflet shared at RESISTIRÉ Final Conference

Moreover, a new digital flyer was also created for broader communication purposes that cover general promotional needs. The flyer outlines key concepts of the project’s identity and scope and it is available at the website’s communication material section [\[link\]](#).

Figure 3. CALIPER new general flyer

2.1.2 Posters and banners

In addition to the new leaflet, new posters were drafted following the same style. The posters were utilised to demonstrate the major outcomes of the first, as well as the second round of GEPs iteration by the CALIPER RPOs/RFOs. They were showcased during events held by sister-projects, namely the [SPEAR](#) and [UNISAFE](#) projects.

CALIPER partners from VIL and SV represented the project in the context of the final conferences of the above-mentioned project, where project poster exhibitions were organised.

Figure 4. CALIPER Poster for the first GEPs round

Figure 5. CALIPER poster for the second GEPs round

What is more, the project delivered a special poster edition for the presentation of a scientific paper co-authored by VIL and SV team members. The paper titled *“It’s all about Priorities: Tips for Successfully Implementing Gender Equality Actions”*, was presented during the paper posters’ exhibition session held within the [6th International Conference on Gender Research - ICGR 2023](#), which took place on 20-21 April 2023 by the Ulster University, Magee Campus in Northern Ireland.

Figure 6. CALIPER paper poster for ICGR 2023

Adding to the above materials, the project drafted a final banner for the promotional purposes of its joint final conference on 23 November 2023. The banner was printed and set at the conference venue along with the banner of the co-organising, sister-project, LeTSGEPs. What is more, a partners’ poster exhibition was hosted as part of the conference activities. More details regarding this activity are provided below.

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

Figure 7. CALIPER final roll-up banner

2.1.3 Infographics

The project has enriched its branding materials, adding two infographics for the purposes of the digital dissemination and target groups engagement of the CALIPER Charter. The infographics are part of the online dissemination of the [CALIPER Charter](#) and help the interested parties to grasp the necessary steps for putting in action the Charter's commitments once they endorse them and for further spreading the word about it, thus broadening its reach.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

Figure 8. CALIPER Charter infographics

2.2 Online channels

2.2.1 CALIPER Website

The project website (<https://caliper-project.eu/>) has served as the focal point for communicating every aspect of CALIPER's actions and outputs. Being under regular monitoring and content management by VIL, that has been collecting project partners' input periodically, the website has undergone improvements since the previously reported period. The aim was to keep up with the project's progress and introduce all the recent project milestones, while updating the layout of key project pages to incentivise a more intuitive and engaging navigation for its users.

In this sense, the homepage of CALIPER website has been updated drawing inspiration from the project's branding and new features have been put forward, such as the Joint Final Conference and the CALIPER Charter.

Figure 9. CALIPER website – new Homepage layout

Figure 10. CALIPER website – new Homepage layout

Furthermore, essential sub-sections like the [policy briefings](#), [helpdesk sessions](#) and [role model interviews](#) pages have been enhanced, while the GEP implementing RPOs/RFOs pages have been re-formatted to accommodate the partners' new achievements. The snapshots below provide a pair of examples from the pages' updates in terms of content and styles.

Policy Briefings

Research findings and experiences gained through the project in relation to the implementation and sustainability of GEPs in STEM RPOs/RFOs

Throughout the project lifecycle, CALIPER disseminates key policy briefings with the aim to **bridge the gap between research and policy for greater gender equality in STEM fields**. The project delivers a series of policy briefings featuring practical recommendations to orientate the development and adoption of measures towards an inclusive GEP. In particular, **three versions of policy briefing** series are envisioned:

1. Policy briefing v1: Focusing on the design and development of a GEP
2. Policy briefing v2: Focusing on the implementation of a GEP
3. Policy briefing v3: Focusing on the Evaluation and assessment of a GEP

Each version entails **10 documents (1 European level and 9 national)** created based on the project's experience of the design and development of CALIPER GEPs by the partner RPOs/RFOs. The policy briefings are **targeted for policy and decision-makers, top management of Higher Education institutions, gender experts and researchers**.

European Level Recommendations

Version 1

National Level Recommendations

Croatia (UZG-FER) Version 1		
Belgium (ULB) Version 1		
Romania (UEFISCDI) Version 1		

Figure 11. CALIPER website – Policy Briefings new layout

CALIPER Role Model Interviews

CALIPER PRO and RFO partners interview exceptional female researchers in their respective areas to create promotional videos thus raising awareness and generating debate about gender inequality issues in STEM fields.

Assoc. Professor Ing. Ivona Čerňáková
Faculty of Materials Science and Technology, Slovak University of Technology

"I would like to introduce science to people in such a way that it reveals the secrets that are part of our lives and the secrets of nature. If a girl likes STEM sciences, she should not be discouraged and guided by prejudices, but follow her feelings!"

[WATCH THE INTERVIEW](#)

ULB Spotlight: Women in STEM
Université Libre de Bruxelles

"Science is not male or female- it is a choice, and it is your choice. It is an infinite universe where we all can always learn more."

[WATCH THE INTERVIEW](#)

Figure 12. CALIPER website – Role Model Interviews new layout

Institute for Research in Biomedicine
Barcelona, Spain - Research Performing Organisation

The Organisation | **Key Ambition**

The Institute for Research in Biomedicine (IRB Barcelona) is an independent, non-profit research institution engaged in basic and applied biomedical science. It was founded by the Government of Catalonia and the University of Barcelona in October 2005 and is member of the CERCA research centres promoted by the former. Housed within the Barcelona Science Park on the University of Barcelona Campus, IRB Barcelona is an integral part of the "Bioregion of Catalonia", a rich landscape of research centres of excellence.

The Institute's missions include conducting multidisciplinary research of excellence at the unique interface between biology, chemistry and medicine, providing high-level training in the biomedical sciences to staff, students and visitors, driving innovation through active technology transfer to the benefit of society, and actively participating in an open dialogue with the public through a series of engagement and education activities.

GEP Library of IRB

Based on the 5-Phases CALIPER work plan, IRB **implements 2 rounds of Gender Equality Plan design, development and evaluation lasting 12 months each**. Substantial results stemming from this process ensure the smooth running of the planned interventions, the engagement and commitment of key stakeholders and the envisioned sustainability of GEPs.

Internal Assessment	External Assessment	Gender Equality Plan	GEP webpage of IRB
A comprehensive analysis of gender equality related conditions within 9 specific areas inside the Institute for Research in Biomedicine in Barcelona	Analysis of external framework conditions & innovation ecosystems from a gender perspective of Institute for Research in Biomedicine in Barcelona.	A set of actions to assess the impact of procedures to identify gender bias; implement strategies to correct any bias; set targets & monitor progress via indicators.	A dedicated page inside the Organisation's web portal presenting GEP activities for internal structural changes towards Gender Equality and collaborations with key external stakeholders.
View	View	View	View

The Research & Innovation Hub of IRB

What is the R&I Hub?

IRB has identified external key players of the regional and national innovation ecosystem, including academia and universities, industry players, ministries/government bodies, and public sector and civil society organisations to engage them in the GEP process.

Engaging interested and key external stakeholders in the GEP processes can bring gender balance and gender sensitiveness in transfer to the market of scientific research results, it motivates young girls to embrace STEM studies, and it promotes gender sensitive co-design of research and tech products.

IRB works with the external players of the Hub, to implement the collaborative GEP actions. These actions facilitate institutional change internally, but also initiate a conversation among the regional and national stakeholders, to adopt and implement gender policies in their organisations.

The R&I Hub members

Figure 13. CALIPER website – GEP implementing partners' page new layout

At this point, it is essential to stress that the CALIPER website is not taken into account as a finalised process. Rather than that, the project website is a key element of the project's exit strategy, for pragmatic and resourceful exploitation and sustainability of CALIPER's key project results. Hence, the website is going to be further updated to entail all the final project results upon their validation by the relevant bodies, either by the European Commission or the institutional senior management of the CALIPER partners, whenever this validation is expected. In this sense, for example, the second and third series of CALIPER policy briefings will be also uploaded and disseminated from the project website, while the GEP implementing partners' pages will be restructured as user-friendly GEP libraries for the interested third parties who seek guidance and best practices regarding the co-design, monitor and evaluate their own GEPs.

The fundamental goal of the website's final renovation upon the project's end is going to transform the website from the central dissemination and communication point to a comprehensive portal of valuable

resources for future projects, initiatives and organisations (especially research-oriented ones) across Europe that work on GEPs implementation. To this end, the CALIPER website is going to feature the following key resources and sections:

- GEP libraries
- CALIPER Charter dedicated sub-section
- Helpdesk sessions presentations and documentation
- Policy briefings
- Role model video Interviews
- Repository of CALIPER public deliverable reports
- FAQ section with informative blog articles

M31-M48 STATISTICS

For the period addressed within the current report, VIL has continued the monitoring of the project website based on the data retrieved from Google Analytics platform. However, it is important to note that during the examined period, this Google service has been modified, with a new version replacing the existing one on July 2023¹. As a result, the data coverage about the website traffic and performance has been split between two datasets, that is, the analytics processed by the previous property and the ones accumulated by the new Google Analytics 4 service.

Hence the above, the current report presents two summaries of the monitored periods that are based on the data retrieved by two sets of services:

July 2022 (M31) to June 2023 (M42)

During the period that the previous Google service was still active, the CALIPER website demonstrated a steady traffic with more than three and a half thousand visitors (3.597 users in total), who engaged with the website sections in over five thousand sessions (5.326 sessions in total). The service defines a session as the event of a user reaching the examined website and associates all of their activity/usage into a session. In this respect, it is important to highlight that the project's website visitors viewed over ten thousand pages in approximate 2-minutes sessions, while each session entailed the viewing of nearly two CALIPER website pages. The snapshot below presents the exact aggregate counts of the website's traffic for the period covered by the old service.

¹[\[GA4\] Introducing the next generation of Analytics, Google Analytics 4](#)

Figure 14. Google Analytics (old version) – Overview of website traffic

In addition to the above, general, reporting, it is essential to examine the acquisition of the visitors’ traffic to identify the starting points, from which the CALIPER website was reached. The data processed by the old version indicate a significant number of direct visitors. However, this did not impact negatively the visitors’ acquisition from organic search, while it is evident that the website was reach by referral from other websites too. The data indicate that quite a lot of users have discovered CALIPER project through its outreach activities and sought the project website out of their own interest.

		Acquisition		
		Users	New Users	Sessions
		3,597	3,563	5,326
1	Direct	1,758		
2	Organic Search	1,332		
3	Referral	464		
4	Social	174		

Figure 15. Visitors’ acquisition

A closer look at the referral statistic makes evident that the visitors who reached CALIPER from other websites were predominantly browsing the websites of the GEP implementing project partners. This finding shows that the project has achieved effective visibility within the involved project institutions. Google Analytics defines a source as the website where users were navigating before landing on the examined one.

<input type="checkbox"/>	Source [?]	Users [?] ↓	New Users [?]	Sessions [?]
		464 % of Total: 12.90% (3,597)	405 % of Total: 11.37% (3,563)	799 % of Total: 15.00% (5,326)
<input type="checkbox"/>	1. ece.ntua.gr	46 (9.45%)	41 (10.12%)	49 (6.13%)
<input type="checkbox"/>	2. ulb.be	45 (9.24%)	41 (10.12%)	49 (6.13%)
<input type="checkbox"/>	3. mtf.stuba.sk	30 (6.16%)	20 (4.94%)	59 (7.38%)
<input type="checkbox"/>	4. fer.unizg.hr	22 (4.52%)	17 (4.20%)	26 (3.25%)
<input type="checkbox"/>	5. polytech.ulb.be	21 (4.31%)	20 (4.94%)	28 (3.50%)
<input type="checkbox"/>	6. sciences.ulb.be	21 (4.31%)	14 (3.46%)	31 (3.88%)
<input type="checkbox"/>	7. politico.eu	17 (3.49%)	17 (4.20%)	18 (2.25%)
<input type="checkbox"/>	8. gep.uefiscdi.ro	15 (3.08%)	13 (3.21%)	17 (2.13%)
<input type="checkbox"/>	9. unisalento.it	11 (2.26%)	10 (2.47%)	18 (2.25%)
<input type="checkbox"/>	10. hrzz.hr	10 (2.05%)	8 (1.98%)	13 (1.63%)

Figure 16. Visitors' referral sources

July 2023 (M43) to December 2023 (M48)

Based on the data drawn from the new, and current, Google Analytics service, it is evident that the project continues a notable traffic acquisition in its website. The overview of the examined period indicates an aggregate volume of nearly two and a half thousand visitors; a number that is relatively even higher compared to the previous period taking into account that the timeframe spans approximately in the last semester. The chart below shows that the project website experienced spikes that can be related with the communication of the project's joint final conference, whose promotion has been one of the primary goals of the dissemination and communication efforts of the project.

Figure 17. Google Analytics (new version) – Overview of website traffic

Again, the engagement statistics present a considerable volume of page views and user activity for the examined period. More than 5 and half thousand views in CALIPER project pages and approximately 16 thousand events have been documented. The Google service identifies all the user activity as an event.

Figure 18. Google Analytics (new version) – Overview of user activity

In order to have a more detailed view of the user activity within the project website, it is essential to enlist the pages and sections with the greater user activity. The list provided by the service indicates that apart from the homepage, which is the initial page where users land, the joint final conference and the CALIPER Charter pages have gained significant traffic. This finding is essential and reflects the outreach efforts made by the dissemination and communication of the project to engage as many external stakeholders as possible with these two outstanding project actions.

<u>PAGE TITLE AND SCREEN CLASS</u>	<u>VIEWS</u>
Caliper Project – Caliper Project	1.9K
Joint Final Conference – Caliper Pro...	615
CALIPER Charter – Caliper Project	563
Role Models – Caliper Project	375
Université libre de Bruxelles – Calip...	244
Project Vision – Caliper Project	143
National Technical University of Ath...	111

Figure 19. Google Analytics (new version) – List of most viewed pages

2.2.2 Social media pages

The project maintained three pages in popular social media platforms. Namely, a Facebook page, a Twitter account and a LinkedIn page. The social media presence of the project has played a significant role in the project's wider reach and to the awareness raising among different target groups regarding the project's key goal to link Research and Innovation with Gender Equality. The promotion of project's updates and partners' activities, notable outputs such project papers and role model interviews, and key messages in the context of Interactional Days were the primary content spread via the CALIPER social media. The already established network of Sister-Projects, as documented in the previous versions of the dissemination and communication activities reporting, and the partners' commitment to act as multipliers of the CALIPER's messages has contributed significantly to reach wide audiences across the different platforms.

The paragraphs below outline key information social media activities based on the statistics, for the current reporting period, provided by the analytics services/interfaces of the three platforms.

Facebook

The Facebook page of the project, [Caliper EU](#), has accumulated 577 total followers by (M48) December 2023, while the current report is being conducted. In what regards the specific activity within the reported period, the project's Facebook page has made 85 posts which have attained more than eleven thousand page reach according to the insights provided by the platform. Facebook refers to reach as the estimate metric for distribution of a page and its content, including posts, stories and ads. It also includes reach from other sources, such as tags, check-ins and page or profile visits. This number also includes reach from posts and stories that were boosted. Reach is only counted once if it occurs from both organic and paid distribution. Furthermore, the CALIPER followers have registered more than 7 hundred interactions with the page's posts. The platform documents posts' interactions taking into account all the likes or reactions, saves, comments and shares made by users minus the number of deleted interactions.

Figure 20. CALIPER Facebook page

Table 1. CALIPER Facebook page – key metrics

Followers (In total)	577
Posts	85
Reach	11.6K
Interactions	713

In terms of the content, the Facebook page featured all the latest news posted at the CALIPER website, which consisted of upcoming activities of the project and/or of the partners; follow-up news pieces about these activities; calls to actions in context-relevant activities by other EU Projects, Initiatives or Institutions; live updates from the partners’ contributions to events (project and third-party events alike); and project-generated content like the role model interview videos, blog/articles and promotional material.

The snapshots below showcase examples of the regular content management of the CALIPER Facebook page’s feed.

Figure 21. CALIPER Facebook – Posts

In regards to the demographics of the CALIPER’s Facebook page followership, female users constitute the approximate 2/3 of the total amount, while the age cohorts are relatively equally distributed even though higher numbers can be found in younger audiences.

Figure 22. CALIPER Facebook – Age and gender of followers

In terms of geographical distribution, the followership consists of primarily the countries represented in the project consortium, with Greece and Italy being the most prominent ones and Georgia and Croatia following.

Figure 23. CALIPER Facebook – Top following countries

Twitter (X)

The Twitter account of the project, [@CaliperEu](#), counts 505 followers in total by the time D6.4 is prepared. Based on the analytics section of Twitter, the profile of the project has reached an estimated 22,35 thousand impressions and documented more than 1,7 thousand engagement actions from the platform users within the covered period. Twitter, defines the impressions as the aggregate number of instances that a tweet appeared on their feed, while it counts the engagement according to all the times the users have interacted with a tweet, including clicking anywhere in the post, such as the featured hashtags, links, avatars and usernames, post's expansion, and reactions (like, comment, repost, follow the profile).

Figure 24. CALIPER Twitter (X)

Table 2. CALIPER Twitter (X) – Key metrics

Followers (In total)	505
Tweets (In total)	597
Impressions	22,35K
Engagement	1749

Following the same purposes as the Facebook page, the Twitter account has also served as a platform to share key messages about the project’s actions, both in project as a whole and at partners’ level, the project synergies with Sister-Projects, as well as live updates from the project’s events and communication material. In the snapshots included below, a few examples of the CALIPER’s tweets are presented:

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

Figure 25. CALIPER Twitter (X) – Tweets

LinkedIn

The LinkedIn page of the project, [Caliper EU](#), has accumulated a total of 313 followers, from several sectors and job functions relevant to the project's scope. Based on the analytics aggregated by the platform for the period reported in this deliverable, the CALIPER posts have reached approximately 24 thousand impressions, which is defined as the views of the post in users' screens. What is more the content posted during this period has collected more than a thousand reactions. LinkedIn platform counts the reactions' number by all the user clicks, such as likes, comments and shares.

Figure 26. CALIPER LinkedIn

Table 3. CALIPER LinkedIn – Key metrics

Followers (In total)	313
Posts	85
Impressions	24,16K
Reactions	1.268

According to the demographic data processed by the analytics of the platform the majority of the CALIPER followers on LinkedIn are employed in research services positions, while persons from job functions at Higher Education, non-profit organisations and governmental sector are also reported.

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

Figure 27. CALIPER LinkedIn – Followers’ job function

In terms of the geographical reach, followers are located predominantly in areas that come from the project partners’ regions, which indicates an efficient dissemination of the project within the ecosystems of CALIPERs’ RPOs and RFOs.

Figure 28. CALIPER LinkedIn – Followers’ location

Aligned with the overall content management approach for CALIPER social media, the LinkedIn page of the project has been posting updates regarding the project’s actions, events and outcomes, as well as original material of the project’s communication efforts and updates from the network of Sister-Projects and EU’s institutions that are relevant to the CALIPER’s scope.

In the snapshots below, regular posts in CALIPER’s feed are provided as an example:

Figure 29. CALIPER LinkedIn – Posts

In addition to the above-described CALIPER social media, it is essential to pay attention to the committed and diligent efforts from the project partners to contribute to the visibility of CALIPER through their own institutional platforms. Project updates regarding particular actions organised at the level of the project partners have been regularly promoted by partners’ social media.

This practise, shared between the partners, enabled the broadening of CALIPER’s reach to greater audiences, since the already established and well-known platforms of the project partners were effective multipliers of the project’s actions, messages and overall vision. From promotion of project actions, synergy activities in bilateral level, or coverage of regional CALIPER activities to articles and publications about and/or facilitated by CALIPER, the project partners demonstrated an exceptional impact to online awareness and visibility goals of the dissemination and communication strategy of the project.

This deliverable entails just a few examples from the partners’ numerous posts about the project throughout the addressed period:

Figure 30. Social media posts by project partners

2.3 Events and networking activities

Within the CALIPER implementation workplan, several events were held in order to address the multifaceted goals of networking, stakeholders’ engagement and raising awareness activities both at the internal (intra-institutional) and the external level. The project DoA entailed many interlinkages across different WPs, namely WP3, WP5 and WP6, whose tasks featured plans for networking activities that would foster

favourable environment for the introduction of GEPs actions and structural change for gender equality in research and innovation ecosystems. In this sense, the dissemination and communication of the project was embedded in multiple events. The organisation of CALIPER helpdesk (training) sessions (T3.1); the plenary GEP WG meetings and briefings with higher/top management councils and committees (T5.3); or the organisation of raising awareness sessions constitute valuable examples of channelling project's knowledge and outcomes to important stakeholders within the CALIPER RPOs/RFOs (T5.3), while the WIN events (T5.2); public info sessions (T6.2); or the CALIPER Charter Webinars (T5.3) are primary reference points of the project's outreach activities.

Hence the above, the dissemination and communication efforts from VIL in collaboration with implementing project partners have been omnipresent across a significant part of their activities. The current deliverable avoids double reporting and exhaustive listing of partners internal meetings and events documented in other deliverables while it focuses on the most prominent CALIPER events that can be considered direct outcomes of the dissemination and communication strategy of the project.

2.3.1 Joint Final Conference

First and foremost, the current reporting period included the biggest of the project's events, the final conference. CALIPER opted to join forces with sister-project, LeTSGEPs to co-hold the event that marked their completion. The event was held on Thursday, 23 November 2023, and it was attended by a total number of 150 people physically and online. The conference was hosted at the ULB premises, and it was titled *"Inclusive Research & Innovation Ecosystems: A sustainable way forward for Gender Equality"*.

Figure 31. CALIPER & LeTSGEPs partners and Conference speakers group photo

The CALIPER partners met with researchers (including post-doc and PhD students), innovation leaders, decision-makers, European Parliament and DG RTD representatives, HR practitioners and Gender Equality experts to highlight the projects' main outcomes, reflect upon shared challenges, as well as actions for achieving long-term, inclusive and sustainable institutional change in terms of gender equality measures and the integration of gender dimension in research.

The conference was unfolded in three key parts. The first part was dedicated to setting the scene and examining the EU's efforts to bring forward meaningful measures for the integration of gender equality in research and innovation via keynote speeches by Lina Gálvez Muñoz from the European Union Parliament and Anne Pepin from DG RTD. The first part also included the overview presentation on the achievements of the two projects in this direction under the scope of their unique project vision.

Figure 32. Conference opening

The second part comprised four consecutive panels inspired by the projects' key topics, that is gender equality and structural change, intersectionality, gender budgeting, and innovation ecosystems' role.

Figure 33. Moments from conference panels

The concluding part entailed the presentation of CALIPER Charter of Gender+ Inclusive R&I Ecosystems. The presentation of the Charter revolved around the fundamental aspects, commitments and calls to action. In addition, the LeTSGEPs Handbook was introduced, a resource developed under the project to provide guidelines for the implementation of GEPs and Gender Budgeting.

Figure 34. Presentation of the CALIPER Charter

Adding to the above keynotes, the recently commenced Sister-Project, [INSPIRE – Centre of Excellence](#), was presented to the audience. The event was finalised with the airing of a project video featuring inspiring stories from women in academic fields that was prefaced by Moniek Tromp, Chair of Materials Chemistry at Groningen University and past-Chair of the Young Academy of Europe.

Figure 35. Joint Final Conference – Role models video

What is more, the event included an exhibition of posters that highlighted the key outcomes and impacts for each GEP implementing project partner.

Figure 36. CALIPER partners from IRB Barcelona in front of their Institution's poster

The summary report as well as the playlist of conference recorded sessions is available at project's website [\[link\]](#).

2.3.2 Webinar - Inclusive Research and Innovation ecosystems in Europe: what works, and how do we convince our stakeholders?

Upon their inclusion in the CALIPER Consortium, CU partners have been assigned with T6.3 – External communication and multiplying effect. To this respect, CU led the organisation of an online event on 7 December 2022 that featured a panel of four experts, representing different sectors and stakeholders, considered what works in achieving an inclusive and interconnected R&I ecosystem. The webinar was chaired by Moniek Tromp, Chair of the Young Academy of Europe (YAE), and the co-organisation was carried out by the AE Cardiff Hub and the Young Academy of Europe for the CALIPER project. Partners from SV and UZG-FER were also involved as panel speakers.

The webinar's panel revolved around three key themes, that is, the creation of a policy framework around the integration of gender equality and inclusivity in research fields, the representation of women scientists in STEM, and the engagement of stakeholders with the participatory processes for the design and implementation of GEPs.

A summary report of the event as well as the complete recordings of the session are available at CU's dedicated website. [\[link\]](#)

Inclusive research and innovation ecosystems in Europe: what works and how do we convince stakeholders?

Webinar, Wednesday 7th December 2022, 12:00 CET (11:00 UK/Ireland)

Welcome and introductions

Moniek Tromp, Chair, Young Academy of Europe

Opening comments from the panel

Marcela Linkova, Head of the Centre for Gender and Science at the Institute of Sociology of the Czech Academy of Science

Maria Sangiuliano, Research Director and Program Manager, Smart Venice/ CALIPER Project Scientific Gender Equality Plans Manager

Professor Anamari Nakic, Assistant professor, CALIPER Project Principal Researcher at UNIZG-FER

Linda Gustafsson, Gender Equality Officer, Umeå kommun

Q&A

Use the Q&A to post concise questions to our panellists. This webinar will be recorded and made available after the event.

Close

“Linking Research & Innovation” and connecting institutional change for gender equality to changes toward more gender Responsive R&I ecosystems: Gender+ inequalities represent joint challenges

WHO_Unbalanced Representation

WHAT_Innovation contents

HOW_Innovation Processes

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 873134

Figure 37. CALIPER Webinar December 2022 – Snapshots

2.3.3 Webinar - Get inspired! How to succeed in your STEM career

In addition to the above, CU lead the organisation of another online event on 17 October 2023, that featured a panel of inspirational women who shared their experiences and advice on addressing the opportunities and challenges of a STEM career.

The webinar was chaired by Dr Gemma Modinos, Reader in Neuroscience & Mental Health, King’s College London and previous Chair of the Young Academy of Europe (YAE). The webinar’s panel comprised three inspirational women, representing different careers stages and areas of expertise, shared their experiences as women in STEM.

The first keynote speaker was Professor Simonetta Manfredi (Oxford Brookes University, UK), who shared the panel with Professor Karine Van Doninck (ULB) and Dr Virginia Petre from University Politehnica of

Bucharest, Romania. Professor Van Doninck and Dr Petre who have made significant contributions to their respective fields, were also role model scientists who participated in the [CALIPER Role Model interviews](#).

During the webinar the speakers shared their experiences and provided invaluable advice on meeting the opportunities and challenges of a STEM career.

A briefing paper about the webinar and the complete recording of the day is available at the CU's dedicated portal [\[link\]](#)

Figure 38. CALIPER Webinar October 2023 – banner

Figure 39. CALIPER Webinar October 2023 – Panel speakers

2.3.4 Partners' activities & Synergies

[Joint online panel discussion with Sister-Project, SPEAR](#)

Date: 10 June 2022 | Location: Rijeka, Croatia | Partner(s): UZG-FER

The UZG-FER partners were invited to an online panel discussion on gender-aware policy in the academic community on the topic “*Everyone’s business: gender equality and the context of higher education*” that took place on June 10, 2022. The panel discussion held in University of Rijeka and within the framework of the Sister-Project, SPEAR.

[Workshop in the context of the 4th Summit on Gender Equality in Computing](#)

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

Date: 16-17 June 2022 | Location: Thessaloniki, Greece | Partner(s): VIL, ECE-NTUA, IRB

The VIL, ECE-NTUA and IRB partners took part in the Summit GEC2022, an annual conference that aims at promoting gender-equal access to the computer-related scientific frontiers, encouraging and educating women and men in an equal way to achieve their goals and utilise their potential in digital professions.

The project partners represented CALIPER within the workshop titled 'Act Together' – The role of H2020 Projects and EU Initiatives & their impact on Gender Equality in STEM, which was organised by Sister-Project RESET. The session brought together 8 Sister-Projects to present their unique impact on the targets and the environments in that they are addressed to.

[Workshop on gender equality in the fields of research and innovation](#)

Date: 30 June 2022 | Location: Zagreb, Croatia | Partner(s): UZG-FER

On Thursday, 30 June, 2022 an online workshop on gender equality in the fields of research and innovation was held at; and it was chaired by Assoc. Ph.D. Brigita Miloš, Faculty of Philosophy, University of Rijeka. The workshop was carried out as part of the project's actions for the implementation of the UZG-FER GEP.

The workshop was targeted to UZG-FER employees, while the main focus was on the following points:

- clarify and discuss basic terms and definitions
- investigate why gender inequality also affects the field of research and innovation: raising awareness of existing inequalities in science, presentation and discussion of statistical data at the European and national level
- acquaint the participants with current policies at the European Union level in the field of research and innovation with an emphasis on three ERA priorities
- present the concept of institutional change, the proposed GEP and the overall scope of the CALIPER project.

[Project contribution at the ELIAMEP Training seminar on Gender Equality Plans \(GEPs\) in Higher Education Institutions](#)

Date: 30 June – 1 July 2022 | Location: Athens, Greece | Partner(s): VIL, ECE-NTUA

The seminar was organized in the framework of the project "Tackling gender inequalities in research and higher education in Greece (GENDRHED)", which is funded by the Active citizens fund programme. The CALIPER partners from VIL and ECE-NTUA took part in the two workshops that comprised the training session and presented the participatory GEP design methodology and the concurrent outcomes within the ECE-NTUA implementation. This training session constituted the first out of four actions entailed by the GENDRHED project; VIL and ECE-NTUA partners contributed to all of the sessions sharing CALIPER's best practises and knowledge that took place at 1-2 December 2022, 23 – 24 February 2023 and 18 – 19 May 2023, respectively.

[Project promotion at ULB booth in the FARI Conference 2022](#)

Date: 5-6 July 2022 | Location: Brussels, Belgium | Partner(s): ULB

The ULB partners set up an exhibition booth for their Institution during the annual FARI Business Conference. The theme of 2022 conference was AI, Data, and Robotics for the Common Good. The ULB partners had focused their booth on the Gender Equality and representation of female scientists in STEM fields to raise awareness regarding this topic.

Figure 40. ULB booth at FARI Business Conference 2022

[Project representation in the context of TAKE 2022 Theory and Applications in the Knowledge Economy, Conference](#)

Date: 6-8 July 2022 | Location: Porto, Portugal (Hybrid) | Partner(s): STU BA

Partners from STU BA participated in the “TAKE 2022 Theory and Applications in the Knowledge Economy” conference that took place in 6th-8th of July 2022 at Porto in Portugal. The conference was hosted by the Universidade de Portucalense, as an international scientific conference devoted to the multidisciplinary study of the knowledge economy. STU BA partners shared their concurrent experience from the GEP Development with a focus on Work-Life Balance.

[Project webinar in the context of EuroScience Open Forum conference, ESOF 2022](#)

Date: 16 July 2022 | Location: Leiden, The Netherlands (Hybrid) | Partner(s): CU, ULB, IRB

Partners from CU AE Cardiff organised a webinar within the conference ESOF 2022. The session addressed challenges faced by women leaders in academia. The titled of the event was “*The Chair: Fact or Fiction? Addressing the challenges faced by women leaders in academia*” drawing from the Netflix comedy-drama, *The Chair*, as a backdrop to the discussion.

During the panel discussions, partners from ULB and IRB CALIPER teams contributed to key topics addressed.

[Project presentation during Researcher’s Night](#)

Date: 29 September 2022 | Location: Athens, Greece | Partner(s): ECE-NTUA

The ECE-NTUA project team prepared a CALIPER presentation for the annual NTUA’s Researcher’s Night event, held at NTUA Patission historic Complex.

Figure 41. CALIPER infographic made by ECE-NTUA for annual Researcher’s Night 2022

Contribution to Workshop in the context of IEEE BHI-BSN 2022 Conference

Date: 27-30 September 2022 | Location: Ioannina, Greece (Hybrid) | Partner(s): ECE-NTUA

The ECE-NTUA partners represented CALIPER in the context of the fifth workshop of the IEEE conference, which was titled “Co-designing for gender equality: towards gender balance in scientific careers, decision making bodies and R&I content.”. The workshop was chaired by Sister-Project, GenderSTI, team members and aimed to identify key issues in aspects related to gender policies and develop potential solutions through a design thinking process in order to contribute to integrate the gender perspective in Science, Technology and Innovation. Participants will discuss opportunities in their country or institution and co-design potential solutions that can be implemented to foment gender equality in the future.

Project representation at the GEARING Roles project final Conference

Date: 18 October | Location: Brussels, Belgium (Hybrid) | Partner(s): SV

The CALIPER scientific coordinators from SV represented the project in the context of the concluding conference of the Sister-Project, GEARING Roles.

[Project representation at the GenderSMART project final Conference](#)

Date: 19 October 2022 | Location: Brussels, Belgium (Hybrid) | Partner(s): SV

The CALIPER scientific coordinators from SV represented the project in the context of the concluding conference of the Sister-Project, GenderSMART.

[Project promotion in the context of the 33rd Annual Conference of Academia Europaea \(AE\) and 11th of the Young Academy of Europe](#)

Date: 26-27 October 2022 | Location: Barcelona, Spain (Hybrid) | Partner(s): CU

Begin a member of Academia Europaea (E), CU partners attended the annual conference of AE, which was held in conjunction with the Young Academy of Europe (YAE). On the first day, the CU partners took part in the special session “Towards an inclusive and representative academic landscape”; while the second day they participated in the special session “YAE Task Forces: Transdisciplinary, Science Outreach, EDI”. On both occasions, the CU partners disseminated the CALIPER’s goals on implementing GEPs, and they showcased their role in the project.

[Workshop jointly organised with Greek IEEE Affinity Group](#)

Date: 3 November 2022 | Location: Online | Partner(s): ECE-NTUA

The ECE-NTUA partners collaborated with [IEEE Greece Section Women in Engineering Affinity Group](#), to co-host a workshop in the framework of the CALIPER project activities. The workshop was titled “Integration of the gender dimension into the research of the Electrical and Computer Engineer”.

Figure 42. ECE-NTUA joint workshop – Poster

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

[Participation at the 4rth Edition of STEM Women Congress](#)

Date: 17 November 2022 | Location: Barcelona, Spain (Hybrid) | Partner(s): IRB

The IRB partners attended the annual Congress of STEM Women on behalf of the project. The event's purpose is to bring together industry, initiatives and research institutions to promote the visibility and the uptake of female scientists in the STEM fields.

[Participation at the roundtable on racial and sex biases in artificial intelligence and medical technologies](#)

Date: 30 November 2022 | Location: Barcelona, Spain (Hybrid) | Partner(s): IRB

The IRB partners represented the CALIPER's scope and impact during the roundtable that was jointly organised by the Department of Information and Communications Technologies of the UPF; Equality, Diversity and Inclusion committee of the Barcelona Biomedical Research Park (PRBB); and Barcelona Supercomputing Centre (BSC).

The joint event discussed how AI can sustain gender, racial and other discriminations, both in medicine and in other fields, and what the impact of these biased algorithms might be. In two round tables, panels of diverse experts discussed what can we do to solve these issues, and to ensure that AI provides the benefits it promises in a fair way for all.

[Project presentation in the context of the 3rd International Congress Of Women In A Global World \(WGW2022\)](#)

Date: 1-2-3 December 2022 | Location: Istanbul, Turkey (Hybrid) | Partner(s): YU

YU partners gave an online presentation about the CALIPER project and their GEP development process at the 3rd International Congress Of Women In A Global World (WGW2022) organized by Topkapı University. The presentation was titled *"Developing Gender Equality Plans For Higher Education Institutions: CALIPER Project Experience"*, and it focused on the internal and external analysis process of YU GEP.

Figure 43. YU presentation at WGW2022

[Project contribution at the PROTAGINISTE 2022 Conference](#)

Date: 6 December 2022 | Location: Lecce, Italy | Partner(s): UNILE

UNILE partners presented the CALIPER project and its impact during the annual open Conference of Salento University.

[Project awareness event on the Elimination of Gender Violence in the Higher Education Institutions](#)

Date: 13 December 2022 | Location: Athens, Greece | Partner(s): ECE-NTUA

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

ECE-NTUA partners joined efforts with the Gender Equality Committee of the university and organised an event on the elimination of gender-based violence in Higher Education Institutions. The main goal of the event was to inform the NTUA community on ways of dealing with incidents of gender violence, the steps required to create a protective framework, what is on place today, as well as exploring proposals to eliminate gender-based violence and/or sexual harassment in Higher Education Institutions. The event had more than 55 on site participants and more than 180 online participants from Greece, Cyprus, Italy and the USA.

[Project representation at the SPEAR project final Conference](#)

Date: 1 March 2023 | Location: Copenhagen, Denmark (Hybrid) | Partner(s): VIL, SV, IRB

The CALIPER team comprised by VIL, SV and IRB partners represented the project in the context of the concluding conference of the Sister-Project, SPEAR.

Figure 44. Social media post from SPEAR final conference

[Project representation at panel discussion of DG RTD](#)

Date: 15 March 2023 | Location: Online | Partner(s): UEFISCDI

Team members from UEFISCDI contributed on behalf of the project at the online roundtable/panel Q&A session organised by DG RTD. The UEFISCDI partners exchanged their CALIPER experience and shared their takes on the role of GEPs at regional research institutions.

[Contribution to joint webinar on inclusive teaching in Higher Education Institutions](#)

Date: 29 March 2023 | Location: Online | Partner(s): ECE-NTUA

ECE-NTUA partners synergised with Women on Top, an established Greek NGO for the professional empowerment of women and equality in the public sphere to hold the event on “Inclusive teaching in Higher Education Institutions: Challenges & Resistances”.

[Joint workshop on Center for Scientific and Technical Information of the Slovak Republic](#)

Date: 13 April 2023 | Location: Trnava, Slovakia | Partner(s): STU BA

CALIPER partners from STU BA team held a meeting with stakeholders from the Center for Scientific and Technical Information of the Slovak Republic (CVTI SR) dedicated to gender equality in STEM research. The topic of the meeting was *“the Gender Equality Plan as eligibility criteria for funding in the Horizon Europe program”*. The STU BA partners presented CALIPER’s GEP implementation and gender dimension integration approaches to the attendees.

[Paper poster exhibition in the context of International Conference on Gender Research – ICGR 2023](#)

Date: 20-21 April 2023 | Location: Derry-Londonderry, Northern Ireland | Partner(s): VIL

The VIL partners, as the co-authors, of paper *“It’s all about Priorities: Tips for Successfully Implementing Gender Equality Actions”*, took part in the ICGR 2023 Conference where they presented the poster of the paper.

Figure 45. VIL Coordination team presented the poster of co-authored CALIPER paper at ICGR 2023

[Project presentation within Girls Day at MTF STU in Trnava](#)

Date: 27 April 2023 | Location: Trnava, Slovakia | Partner(s): STU BA

CALIPER partners from STU BA team prepared a presentation titled [“How we work with gender equality at MTF STU in Trnava”](#) to present the project at young students within the annual open-day event jointly-organised by civil society organisation Aj Ty v IT and the Faculty of STU BA.

[Project representation at the context of IEEE ICASSP 2023 Progress Workshop](#)

Date: 4-10 June 2023 | Location: Rhodes, Greece | Partner(s): ECE-NTUA

ECE-NTUA partners participated in the IEEE ICASSP PROGRESS (PROmoting DiveRsity in Signal ProceSSing) Workshop on the 4th of June 2023, in Rhodes Greece. The ECE-NTUA partners moderated and participated the panel on *“Efforts in Promoting Diversity and Inclusion in Signal Processing and Engineering”*.

[Project introduction during presentation of book 'Doppio Standard'](#)

Date: 12 June 2023 | Location: Lecce, Italy | Partner(s): UNILE

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

UNILE project team presented the project during a book presentation event in the University of Salento. The book was titled *“Doppio Standard”*, that is, “Double Standard” and focuses on the careers of female researchers and scientists in the contemporary Italy. The UNILE partners were part of the event’s panel.

[Project representation at the RESISTIRÉ project final Conference](#)

Date: 20-21 June 2023 | Location: Brussels, Belgium [Hybrid] | Partner(s): VIL

The CALIPER coordinators from VIL represented the project in the context of the conference organised by the Sister-Project, RESISTIRÉ.

[Project representation at the launching event of G-WISE Network](#)

Date: 29 June 2023 | Location: Online | Partner(s): ECE-NTUA

Project partners from ECE-NTUA synergised with Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH), partners of Sister-Project, RESET, to establish a Greek network of Women in STEM & Entrepreneurship. The network kick-started its activities with a launching event on the 29th of June. Representatives from ATHENA Research Center, also, contributed to the establishing event.

[Session chair and keynote speech at The Migration Conference 2023](#)

Date: 23-26 August 2023 | Location: Hamburg, Germany (Hybrid) | Partner(s): YU

During the first day of the TMC 2022, the YU partners chaired a session dedicated to the Education and Skilled Migration, in which they also gave a keynote speech under the topic *“Diversity and Gender Equality Plans for Managing Diversity and Preventing Discrimination in Higher Education Institutions”*.

[Project representation during the Open Debate on Gendered Innovation Living Labs by Sister-Project GiLL](#)

Date: 21-23 September 2023 | Location: Barcelona, Spain (Hybrid) | Partner(s): IRB

The Sister-Project GiLL held an open debate regarding gendered innovation through Living Labs as part the Open Living Lab Days 2023 (OLLD2023) in the city of Barcelona. The session provided over 50 attendees with insights into how effectively the Living Lab approach and methods/tools can support the transition into a more just world, not only for women, but also looking into diversity and inclusion of minorities in STEM careers. The IRB partners were part of the panel and addressed the integration of gender equality and gender dimension in research organisations through the lenses of the CALIPER project experience.

[Project representation during the book presentation/seminar Women? Men? Sex and gender, biology and culture](#)

Date: 22 September 2023 | Location: Barcelona, Spain (Hybrid) | Partner(s): IRB

The IBMB Diversity, Inclusion and Equity (DEI) Committee, in coordination with the Equality and Diversity Committee of IRB, organized the presentation of a book written by Jordi Casanova i Roca, Professor of Investigation of CSIC and PI at IBMB and IRB. The CALIPER project team of IRB attended the event on behalf of the project.

[Project representation at the Sister-Project, INSIRE, Conference](#)

Date: 5-6 October 2023 | Location: Budapest, Hungary (Hybrid) | Partner(s): SV

The CALIPER scientific coordinators from SV represented the project in the context of the conference organised by the Sister-Project, INSPIRE.

[Project presentation at the International E+ seminar in Zagreb](#)

Date: 15 November 2023 | Location: Zagreb, Croatia | Partner(s): UZG-FER

Project partners from UZG-FER organised a study visit as part of the Seminar “Embrace Inclusion and Diversity in your Erasmus+ Projects!”. The event was organized by the Agency for Mobility and EU Programs. The visit was organized on November 15, 2023, and 20 participants from European universities participated. The project partners presented the GEP implementation procedures applied in UZG-FER in the context of CALIPER project.

[Project representation at the PRISMA Conference](#)

Date: 16-17-18 November 2023 | Location: Madrid, Spain (Hybrid) | Partner(s): IRB

The IRB partners took part in the annual Conference planned by the Spanish organisation, PRISMA-Asociación para la Diversidad Afectivo-Sexual y de Género en Ciencia, Tecnología e Innovación. The IRB team members gave a keynote presentation regarding the CALIPER’s impact and outcomes for the IRB institution.

[Project representation at the Sister-Project, UNISAFE final conference](#)

Date: 21-22 November 2023 | Location: Namur, Belgium (Hybrid) | Partner(s): VIL, SV

The CALIPER project management and scientific coordination teams from VIL and SV represented the project in the context of the concluding conference of the Sister-Project, UNISAFE.

Figure 46. VIL and SV partners presenting CALIPER impact poster at UNISAFE final conference

[Project representation at the first award ceremony of the Executive Master S.He goes digital](#)

Date: 24 November 2023 | Location: Brussels, Belgium (Hybrid) | Partner(s): ULB

The ULB hosted the inaugural ceremony of awards for the Executive Master S.He goes digital. The event is of key importance in the joint efforts of ULB, via its Continuing Education for Technology and Science (TechSci),

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in collaboration with the VUB, Febelfin and Agoria; and it has been Initiated to meet the major challenges of finding IT talent and promoting diversity. It is an initiative designed to meet the major challenges of finding talent in IT and promoting diversity in this strategic sector. The ULB partners presented CALIPER project during the event to increase the awareness of the Institution's GEP actions.

[Project presentation at the PROTAGONISTE 2023 Conference](#)

Date: 28 November 2023 | Location: Lecce, Italy | Partner(s): UNILE

UNILE partners presented the CALIPER project and its impact during the annual open Conference of Salento University.

Project presentation at the International Conference on Global Studies (IC-GS-23)

Date: 11 December 2023 | Location: Edinburg, UK | Partner(s): STU BA

STU BA partners presented the gained experience and best practices in the implementation of GEP at MTF STU as part of the CALIPER project.

2.4 Publications

Over the course of its duration, CALIPER put forward multiple public deliverables and scientific publications that channelled project objectives, its plan of action and key outcomes for the integration of gender equality and the gender dimension in research. The project maintains a dedicated [repository at the Zenodo platform](#) where public outputs like deliverables, presentations, and papers of the project are accessible. The repository is updated in periodic phases. Upon the validation of the final project results (i.e., deliverables and project efforts) the Zenodo repository is going to feature the remaining public outputs in order to afford a complete set of resources for interested groups including GEP implementing research organisations, gender experts and future projects and/or initiatives.

2.4.1 Scientific/academic and technical Publications

In terms of scientific/academic and technical publications the project has conducted seven publications within the covered period. The table below aggregates these publications and gives an overview of basic information, including their publication dates, the identification of corresponding partners and the publishing body.

Table 4. CALIPER scientific/academic and technical publications – M31-M48

<i>Title of publication</i> <i>(Conference papers, abstracts, peer-reviewed articles, book chapters, etc.)</i> <i>DOI (if applicable)</i>	<i>Publication date</i>	<i>Authoring partners</i>	<i>Publisher</i>
Spatial Olfactory Memory and Spatial Olfactory Navigation, Assessed with a Variant of Corsi Test, Is Modulated by Gender and Sporty Activity https://doi.org/10.3390/brainsci12081108	Aug 2022	UNILE	Brain Sciences, Special Issue Chemosensory Perception and Chemosensory Cognition MDPI
Legal feasibility study related to the adoption of positive actions in favour of women in STEM	Sep 2022	ULB	Equality Law Clinic (ELC)

			ULB
Chemobrain, Olfactory and Lifestyle Assessment in Onco-Geriatrics: Sex-Mediated Differences between Chemotherapy and Immunotherapy https://doi.org/10.3390/brainsci12101390	Oct 2022	UNILE	Brain Sciences, Special Issue Chemosensory Perception and Chemosensory Cognition MDPI
It's all about Priorities: Tips for Successfully Implementing Gender Equality Actions https://doi.org/10.34190/icgr.6.1.1006	Apr 2023	SV & VIL	Proceedings of the 6 th International Conference on Gender Research Academic Conferences International (ACI)
Developing Gender Equality Plans for Higher Education Institutions: CALIPER Project Experience ISBN: 9781801352208	May 2023	YU	Women in a Globalizing World – IV: Empowerment and Challenges (Book) Transnational Press London
Diversity and Gender Equality Plans for Managing Diversity and Preventing Discrimination in Higher Education Institutions Digital ISBN: 978-1-80135-232-1	Aug 2023	YU	The Migration Conference 2023 Book of Abstracts Transnational Press London
Setting up inclusive Gender Equality Plans - the CALIPER experience (Abstract) https://bmcproc.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12919-023-00275-w#Sec203	Oct 2023	VIL & SV	Abstracts from the International Conference Diversity Interventions 2022 BMC Proceedings

2.4.2 Briefing papers

Further to the above-listed publications, it is important to note that the project reports additional publications of significant value. These publications include the first series of CALIPER policy briefings, briefing papers from CU and the contribution of IRB's project partners to a Manifesto issued by the 'Women and Science Commission' of the Inter-University Council of Catalonia.

CALIPER Policy Briefings v1

Upon their approval from EC corresponding bodies, the first series of policy briefs that CALIPER has drafted within the *D6.5 – Policy Briefings v1*, have been integrated into a new project report template for popularized publications. This way, these key project results have been disclosed to the general public following a more simplified, yet engaging, format. The first series of CALIPER policy briefs consists of a document targeted at pan-European Level and nine documents that correspond to the countries represented by the RPOs/RFOs of the project. These documents are accessible via their dedicated page on the project website [[link](#)]. Once the second and third policy briefings deliverables are validated, the relevant materials will also be disseminated to the external target audiences in a similar fashion.

Figure 47. CALIPER Policy Briefings v1 – Snapshots from European and National documents

CU Briefing papers

Following the organisation of their assigned webinars, the CU partners drafted standardised briefings that documented the aftermath of these events. As a result, two briefing papers were posted by CU at their website and communicated by the partner’s online channels. The first one summarised the online panel discussion held on 7 December 2022 (see 2.3.2 section) [\[link\]](#), while the second one covered the webinar organised on 17 October 2023 (see 2.3.3 section) [\[link\]](#).

Figure 48. CU Briefing paper about CALIPER webinar

PRISMA Guidelines for LGBTQIA+ equality in research centres and STEM environments

After the successful organisation of a helpdesk session (17 May, 2023) CALIPER project and [PRISMA Association](#) took their synergy a step forward. Sharing the belief that research centres can serve as a model for justice, equality, and diversity the synergy advocates for equal opportunities, safe spaces, visibility, and high-quality scientific production. In this respect, CALIPER project provided technical and financial assistance to PRISMA Association to put forward an English publication consisting of 10 actions to improve the reality of the LGBTQIA+ community in research centres and science, technology, and innovation environments, as well as its Implementation Guide. These 10 basic actions are supported by statistical data demonstrating their urgent need, and they can contribute to building better and more just scientific spaces.

The guide can be accessed via a dedicated post at CALIPER website. [\[link\]](#)

Figure 49. PRISMA Guide for LGBTQIA+

Manifesto for the Eradication of Sexist Violence in Universities and Research Centers

In the context of 25 November, the International Day for the Elimination of Violence against Women, the Government of the Generalitat de Catalunya issued a Manifesto document to mitigate the gender-based-violence phenomena in Universities and Research Centers of the region. The document was elaborated by the 'Women and Science Commission' of the Inter-University Council of Catalonia.

Being a key member of the research and innovation ecosystem of the region, IRB was onboarded on the preparatory procedures that delivered the Manifesto. The CALIPER experience, concurrent findings and best practises were taken into account for the proposition of the values and the commitments of the document [\[link\]](#).

2.5 Media content

During the period covered by the current deliverable, the project has issued several communication materials in different media content formats. What is more, the project partners have demonstrated notable efforts to act as multipliers of the CALIPER messages and outputs via the publication of media content through their own channels.

2.5.1 Newsletters, press releases and news posts

Within the reported period of this deliverable, four new project newsletters were published to communicate concurrent developments and invite project's target audiences to engage with CALIPER activities. The newsletters were issued using the established Mailchimp account of the project that counts 232 contacts. Upon their circulation, the issues have been posted at the project website dedicated page [\[link\]](#) and shared via the project's social media. By the time the current deliverable is prepared, the project counts 9 original newsletter issues. It is important to note that, an additional newsletter issue is going to be published to communicate the official completion of the project, as part of the overall exit strategy of the project.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

Figure 50. CALIPER newsletters – Snapshots from the 6th and 8th issues

What is more, the communications activities were also supported by tailored email promotions circulated by project coordinator, VIL, and scientific coordinator, SV, among the Sister-Projects network comprising more than 30 EU-funded projects for Gender Equality in research and innovation. That is, VIL and SV contacted the leading teams of the Sister-Projects to share important news from CALIPER's advancements in regular basis, a common-practise shared among the network to sustain awareness and prompt the collaboration and mutual support of the projects' efforts.

Figure 51. Email communications with Sister-Projects – Invitation to endorse the CALIPER Charter

The tailored email communications were also applied to spread the word about the joint final conference of the project. Once the messages were finalised among the organisation teams of CALIPER and LeTSGEPs

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

projects, template emails were drafted and forwarded to Sister-Projects contacts, as well as to the people registered via the event page on Eventbrite platform [[link](#)]. The following snapshots provide an example of such efforts.

Figure 52. CALIPER & LeTSGEPs invitation email sent to Sister-Projects

Figure 53. CALIPER & LeTSGEPs email sent to online registrants

Moreover, the CALIPER news was distributed to a wide range of audiences thanks to the diligent communication that project partners have planned and carried out via their own newsletters, as well as the contributions coming from EC bodies. To this end, 6 newsletter issues published by project partners during the addressed period and one from European Research Executive Agency (REA), resulting in 20 outputs in total from external online platforms mentioning CALIPER project activities and significant moments. All the external newsletters that featured CALIPER have been embedded to the project's dedicated page as well [\[link\]](#).

In regard to the press releases, the project has released one more press release on 20 April 2023 to officially disseminate the publication of its first series of policy briefs; and a press release on 19 December 2023 that summarised the successful organisation of the project's joint final conference. The dedicated page on the project website [\[link\]](#) counts a total of 25 press releases throughout the project duration. What is more, a final, closing, press release is going to be drafted upon the completion of the project to formally communicate that the CALIPER project has come to a full circle. The press release is going to feature the most prominent project's impacts and outcomes and it is going to be shared among project partners so that it is translated into their native languages and shared among their platforms. Furthermore, the press release is going to be forwarded to the EC channels for dissemination at European level.

Adding to the above-described efforts, the GEP implementing RPO/RFOs of the project have published a variety of news posts about their actions within the CALIPER project, thus fostering a meaningful awareness level among their ecosystems. These efforts reflect the notable involvement of partners with the internal and external communication purposes of the relevant WP6 tasks and have a direct contribution from the WP3 and WP5 efforts. The news items from the project partners revolved around the outcomes of their GEP-related activities; and they were posted at partners' institutional portals. Being encouraged to make an impact on their local ecosystem, many of these news items were published in native languages.

National Technical University of Athens
School of Electrical and Computer Engineering

Education	Research	People	School
Undergraduate	Impact	Academic	History
Postgraduate	Laboratories	Laboratory	Organization
Doctoral	ICCS	Research	Access
ERASMUS	Libraries	Administrative	Contact

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Training Workshop on the application of the “Guide for the use on non sexist language in the administrative documents”

On Thursday 7th of July 2022, 10.00, a training workshop took place for the application of the “Guide for the use on non sexist language in the administrative documents”.

The “Guide for the use on non sexist language in the administrative documents” was implemented in 2018, by the Ministry of Interior in collaboration with the General Secretariat for Demography and Family Policy and Gender Equality.

Its main goal is to contribute towards the identification of verbal sexism, as well as to provide guidance, examples, advice and recommendations on the use of non sexist language, towards the promotion and integration of the gender equality dimension in the administrative documents.

The training workshop on the application of the Guide addressed to all the administrative personnel of the School, while its main objectives were:

- Increased familiarity with the use of the Guide,
- Application of the Guide in the administrative documents of the School and in its communication with the external environment

The training workshop consisted of two Sessions:

- A theoretical session: Introducing the main topics addressed in the Guide,
- A practical session: Studying the respective adjustment of a sample of administrative documents, as well as other communication methods.

Please find attached the “Guide for the use on non sexist language in the administrative documents”, as well as the event’s [presentation](#).

შოთა რუსთაველის საერთაშორისო ეროვნული სამეცნიერო ფონდი
SHOTA RUSTAVELI NATIONAL SCIENCE FOUNDATION OF GEORGIA
მეცნიერების, მოავლერძების, სპორტისა და ადამიანთა განვითარების

საგარეო ურთიერთობების სამსახური

შეიარაღი პროგრამები ჩვენს შესახებ მხედველობა მოსახლეობის სტატისტიკა საჯარო ინფორმაცია საერთაშორისო ურთიერთობები კონტაქტი EN

პროექტი CALIPER

შეიარაღი > საერთაშორისო ურთიერთობები > CALIPER > პროექტი CALIPER

CALIPER –

პროექტი CALIPER

გენდერული თანასწორობის გეგმა (GEP)

ETHICS +

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TWINNING +

გენდერული თანასწორობა

შოთა რუსთაველის ეროვნული მეცნიერების ფონდის „კორინტი 2021“-ის CALIPER პროექტის ფარგლებში შემუშავდა გენდერული თანასწორობის გეგმა, რომელიც მიზნად ისახავს გენდერული თანასწორობის უზრუნველყოფას ექვსი სფეროსა და მხარეებში.

YASAR UNIVERSITY
Jam Mevlevi Center of Excellence (JM Centre)

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CALIPER Project Sustainability Workshop

 0 Comment

On November, 28th, 2022 CALIPER Project Sustainability Workshop was organized by Yasar University JM Centre of Excellence (EU Center). The workshop is aimed at facilitating the process of elaborating the Sustainability Plan for the Yasar University Gender Equality Plan (GEP) which is developed within the scope of the CALIPER project. Among the workshop participants, there were members of the GEP working group, middle and high management, HR and gender equality officers, and other internal stakeholders supporting the GEP implementation.

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

Figure 54. News items about CALIPER GEP actions in partners platforms

2.5.2 Interviews, blogs and podcasts

The project put emphasis on outreach activities and the promotion of the CALIPER vision to the scientific community and general audiences alike. Adding to the communication materials reported above, the project demonstrated several interviews, blog articles and podcasts that addressed the scope of the project and shared insights focusing on the GEPs role, the need and the added value of gender equality and gender dimension in research. In this context, the following dissemination and communication materials were produced:

Project coordinator, Kyriaki Karydou of VIL, gave an interview at the NCP_WIDER.NET project in the context of a publication that put the spotlight on EU-funded projects that reform and enhance the European Research & Innovation ecosystems [\[link\]](#).

Figure 55. Kyriaki Karydou's interview at NCP_WIDERA.NET publication

Another interview that facilitated CALIPER's scope was carried out by IRB partners. The project team of IRB has coordinated the organisation of an interview for the celebration of the 2023 International Day of Women and Girls in Science. The IRB produced a promo interview featuring the young researcher Sandra Blázquez, a PhD student at IRB's Inflammation, Tissue Plasticity and Cancer lab, being interviewed by three pupils from Institute Angelata Ferrer in Barcelona.

The interview took place in the facilities of IRB, where the young students had the opportunity to experience a day in work of Ms Blázquez and ask her many questions about her motives, her dreams and challenges in her field. The interview is available at the IRB's YouTube channel [\[link\]](#)

Drawing inspiration from the CALIPER Role Model Interview's (as reported in the corresponding *D6.7 – Role model's report*), CU and ULB partners have launched their own dedicated sections on their institutional platforms, where interviews and stories about remarkable scientists that positively impacted the advancement of gender equality and the role of female researchers in science are published.

The CU section is titled "*Gender Equality Interview Series*" [\[link\]](#) and features 12 interview pieces. The editorial includes the transcribed interviews of several CALIPER role models, as well as additional interviews with key individuals who come from Academia Europaea and the Young Academy of Europe, both pan-European networks with a combined membership of about 6,000 outstanding scientists and scholars.

The ULB section is titled "*Scientific Woman of the Week*" [\[link\]](#) and covers the stories of exceptional female researchers and scientists in weekly basis. This initiative sought to turn the spotlight on those pioneering women who changed the world of science and society – from Nobel laureates; to space explorers; down to the smallest yet incredibly impactful molecular discoveries.

What is more, during the period covered in the current report, the UZG-FER partners have been engaged with the creation of 4 new episodes of their collaborative podcast, ŽensCast! The podcast was created in collaboration with employees of UZG-FER and members of the Women in Engineering Affinity group of the

Croatian IEEE section. Hosted by the president of WIE IEEE Croatia Assoc. Prof. Ph.D. Pina Milišić, ŽensCast was created as part of the CALIPER and the implementation of UZG-FER's GEP.

The new episodes have reached over a thousand views in the YouTube channel of UZG-FER, thus promoting the role of women in the Engineering fields and inspiring further young students to with the RPO's STEM faculties. All the episodes are posted to the dedicated website managed by UZG-FER project team [[link](#)].

Figure 56. ŽensCast Podcast – Cover image of episode 7

The project has also worked on the delivery of blog articles that can be used as reference points for all the audiences interested in, or already engaged with, the implementation of a GEP. VIL and CU partners have collaborated on the preparation of two blog articles posted at the CALIPER website, under the guidance of SV, as the scientific coordinator of the project, while feedback was also collected by the GEP implementing partners of the project.

As a result, the first blog titled “*Cultivating Collective Innovation: The Power of Co-Design for Structural Change*” [[link](#)] and revolves around the co-design and participatory approaches to the formulation of a GEP that foster collective creativity and greater inclusion of various actors, knowledges, hierarchical levels, and sectors in a GEP design ensuring diversity in the structural change process.

Figure 57. CALIPER Blog – Cultivating collective innovation

The second blog is titled “*How can an organisation effectively assess their Gender Equality Plan?*” [[link](#)] and elaborates on the project's applied methodology for monitoring and assessing a GEP within a research

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

organisation. This evaluation process not only aids organisations in identifying areas for improvement, but also serves as a base for outlining collaborative efforts among GEP Working Groups or partnerships within institutions.

Figure 58. CALIPER Blog – How can an organisation effectively assess their GEP?

2.5.3 Videos

The project maintains a YouTube channel where all the video materials created in the context of the project are publicly available. The channel entails 30 videos that count more than two a half thousand views in total. Approximately half these of videos belong to the role model interviews series (12 videos). The detailed documentation of these video interviews is available in the corresponding *D6.7 – Role models' report*. The recorded sessions of the joint final conference of the project are also published in a dedicated playlist (13 videos), thus allowing viewers to watch the event on demand [\[link\]](#).

Figure 59. Joint Final Conference – YouTube playlist

3 Monitoring and evaluation

The following table summarises the aggregate of the dissemination and communication actions that were carried throughout CALIPER project lifecycle. The clustering corresponds to the KPIs set by the project's GA, while the data presented reflect the reporting presented above, in combination with the data reported within the previous reporting periods in order to provide an overview of the dissemination and communication activities performance from M1 to M48.

Table 5. Dissemination and communication KPIs overview table

Channel	Tool	KPI description	Total for M1-M48
Media	Press release	Total of 25	20
Online channels	Website	Take website live featuring information about the project and update the content periodically	Homepage layout has been revised and new sections have been added. Plan for delivering an overall repository for project's final results has been outlined
	Project publications	At least 3 publications per year.	11 scientific publications (excluding project's public deliverables available at Zenodo repository)
	Newsletter	1 Issue every 6 months.	9 Project Issues published 19 External Issues published featuring CALIPER 1 Newsletter for the project's completion in progress
	Social media	Total of 1,000 followers.	1395 followers across 3 platforms
Offline activities	Promotion materials (brochures, posters, etc.)	Create project's brochure and prepare more materials according to project's needs.	2 Leaflets, 1 Flyer, 2 Project Posters, 1 Banner, 1 Paper Poster, 2 Infographics, 9 Posters for CALIPER RPOs/RFOs
	Conference presentations	>10 presentations along the project	41 Project presentations/contributions within 3rd party conferences
	Collaboration with other EU funded projects/initiatives	>4 collaborations	Sister-Projects network established including 30 funded projects/initiatives 1 Joint Final Conference with LeTSGEPs H2020 Project

4 Conclusion and next steps

The present deliverable is the third, and final report of the project's dissemination and communication efforts. It provides a comprehensive overview of CALIPER Consortium's effort to disseminate and communicate the project to the internal as well as external target audiences, covering the period from M31 – July 2022 to M48 – December 2023.

D6.4 concludes the CALIPER's lifecycle and documents all the relevant outreach and engagement activities both at project level and from each partner's side. Building upon the impact achieved through the previous periods, the project has been progressively working towards the completion of its goals and fostering a lasting effect around the CALIPER GEPs.

The CALIPER partners reported strong commitment to the dissemination and communication efforts, as these were intrinsic to their goals according to their assignments across multiple project WPs and to the goals stemming from their GEPs. Engaging with internal stakeholders to pave the way for structural changes; synergising with their innovation ecosystems to ensure knowledge diffusion and broader collaboration; and making sure that project's KPIs were met adequately, were the driving force of the activities reported in the above sections. The documented data demonstrate that the dissemination and communication of the project were interlinked with actions organised within the CALIPER GEP implementing RPOs/RFOs. These have been multifaceted and directed towards the varying target audiences through multiple channels and formats and reflective of the project's best practices and acquired knowledge.

As the project comes to a full circle the dissemination and communication activities reporting takes into account the importance of ensuring the sustainability of the project's key messages, results and best practices. In this respect, the deliverable concludes with a set of proposed actions after the project's completion that constitute a well-rounded exit strategy. The proposed actions are listed as follows:

- Update the CALIPER website and set up a project repository that grants access to the project's key resources:
 - GEP libraries
 - CALIPER Charter dedicated sub-section
 - Helpdesk sessions presentations and documentation
 - Policy briefings
 - Role model video Interviews
 - Repository of CALIPER public deliverable reports
 - FAQ section with informative blog articles
- Draft a closing CALIPER newsletter and a press release and disseminate the documents to the project partners R&I Hubs stakeholders, Sister-Projects network and EC Bodies.
- Upon their approval, disseminate the CALIPER second and third series of Policy Briefs.
- Update project's Zenodo community with the final set of project's public deliverables, open access publications and presentations.

Annex I: Partners Posters for Joint Final Conference

JOINT FINAL CONFERENCE

INCLUSIVE RESEARCH AND INNOVATION ECOSYSTEMS A SUSTAINABLE WAY FORWARD FOR GENDER EQUALITY

The University of Zagreb established in 1669 is the oldest and biggest university in South-Eastern Europe. The Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computing (FER) is **the largest technical faculty and leading educational and research & development institution in the fields of electrical engineering, information and communication technology and computing** in the Republic of Croatia.

UZG - FER designed, implemented and evaluated its **first Gender Equality Plan within the CALIPER project** and it was the **leading partner assigned with the overview of the implementation of GEPs** by the project partners

PROJECT PARTNER

FIRST GENDER EQUALITY PLAN IMPLEMENTED

At its 710th meeting on 15 September 2021, the Faculty Council adopted **the first Gender Equality Plan**. The proposed measures are based on the results of an analysis into gender equality at FER and in the local and national environment in which the Faculty operates.

STRONG INSTITUTIONAL SUPPORT FOR GENDER EQUALITY

Key factors for obtaining strong institutional support for gender equality included **encouraging personal engagement of employees in the process** from the beginning; dedicated **working group** consisting of influential employees to develop our GEP; **evidence-based arguments to support GEP**; and the support from the high management and EU perspective.

EQUAL OPPORTUNITIES COMMITTEE ESTABLISHED

The Faculty Council **established a permanent Equal Opportunities Committee**. The Committee is responsible for the implementation of GEP and the Diversity and Inclusion Plan.

PROGRESS OF WOMEN'S CAREERS AT UZG-FER

Female students make up 20% of the student population in all studies, undergraduate, graduate and doctoral. A similar percentage of women occupy academic positions at FER. Although the total number of women didn't grow, there are some advances: **women are more represented in managerial positions** and each of the 12 departments now has **at least one female professor**.

CAPACITY BUILDING ACTIVITIES

Through the CALIPER project many resources and activities were organised to ensure the successful implementation of our first GEP. CALIPER's activities provided **training, support and guidance** to build institutional capacity for gender equality.

JOINT FINAL CONFERENCE

INCLUSIVE RESEARCH AND INNOVATION ECOSYSTEMS

A SUSTAINABLE WAY FORWARD FOR GENDER EQUALITY

The **Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava (STU)**, the largest and most significant university of technology in the Slovak Republic, is a modern European educational and research institution. It offers university education mainly in technical, technological, technical-economic, technical-information and technical-artistic fields of study.

In Slovakia's Academic Ranking and Rating Agency, the STU faculties have been regularly awarded the first place rankings. Thanks to the CALIPER project, STU became **one of the research institutions implementing the principle of gender equality in EU conditions.**

SLOVAK UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY IN BRATISLAVA
FACULTY OF MATERIALS SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY IN TRNAVA

PROJECT PARTNER

GENDER EQUALITY COUNCIL ESTABLISHED

For the field of Institutional Management, we have incorporated the **Gender Equality Council**, whose goal is the **sustainability of the Gender Equality Plan (GEP) for the period after the implementation of the CALIPER project.** The Council aims to increase awareness of gender equality for employees, students, external stakeholders, and the University.

INTEGRATION OF GENDER DIMENSION IN ALL STAGES OF RESEARCH

We realised the importance of **implementing gender equality in the project proposals, teaching syllabi, and students' final theses.** In research, we promote gender equality by providing women with **tailored professional support for career growth.** Responsibility towards employment imbalance has become our commitment in the strategic plan of the University.

KEY HIGHLIGHT 5

With the help of the ecosystem, we organised **new seminars and workshops to raise awareness of gender equality among internal stakeholders.** The next level of cooperation was assistance in creating internal guidelines implementing gender equality with a commitment to sustainability and making the necessary resources. The changes perceived as a result of GEP implementation **positively influenced the University's internal culture.**

ENGAGEMENT OF EXTERNAL STAKEHOLDERS FOR THE PARTICIPATORY APPROACH OF GEP DESIGN

The creation and involvement of the ecosystem in the design and implementation of the GEP brought an increase in the quality of the University's internal environment and improved communication skills concerning the university's external environment. We have adopted the practice of using gender-sensitive language.

INCREASE OF FEMALE STUDENTS INTERACTION WITH STEM FIELDS

We have implemented **new initiatives to increase female student enrolment.** The Faculty of Materials Science and Technology recently updated its website's **communication strategy**, which was the first faculty of STU to implement GEP. We organise promotional events targeting girls and engaging them in various activities.

CALIPER project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 873134

JOINT FINAL CONFERENCE

INCLUSIVE RESEARCH AND INNOVATION ECOSYSTEMS A SUSTAINABLE WAY FORWARD FOR GENDER EQUALITY

The Shota Rustaveli National Science Foundation of Georgia (SRNSFG) is a **Legal Entity of Public Law under the aegis of the Ministry of Education, Science, Culture and Sport of Georgia**, which supports the development of Science, Technology and Innovation (STI) system in Georgia. Through the CALIPER project, SRNSFG delivered a Gender Equality Plan (GEP) to introduce gender equality inside the organisation and foster implement structural changes in order to increase the number of female researchers in STEM, improve their careers prospects and integrate a gender dimension in research and innovation in the national ecosystem.

PROJECT PARTNER
CALIPER
Gender Equality in STEM Research

FIRST GENDER EQUALITY PLAN IMPLEMENTED

In SRNSFG, the **first Gender Equality Plan (GEP)** was implemented on the organisational level. The established GEP is helping us making the foundation more gender equal and promote a greater engagement of female researchers with research and innovation.

SPECIAL AWARD FOR FEMALE SCIENTISTS INTRODUCED

The organisation established a **special award dedicated to women scientists!** The goal is to encourage women scientists and research activities by annually introducing successful women scientists to the wider community in Georgia.

SEXUAL HARASSMENT POLICY ADOPTED

The organisation drafted and put in place a **formal set of measures** in order to ensure that all employees are aware of and understand the organisation's **policy regarding sexual harassment**. The policy aims to help SRNSFG maintain a work environment free of sexual harassment and gender-based discrimination, violence and any relevant negative phenomena.

GENDER-RELATED GUIDELINES FOR EVALUATORS SHARED

A set of guidelines and useful instructions that take into account **gender dimension was formulated and provided to evaluators and evaluation committees.** These guidelines are used to prepare evaluators and committee members for a more transparent and gender bias-free evaluation process.

INCREASED VISIBILITY OF GEORGIAN WOMEN IN STEM

A **special section on the organisation's website** was created. The section promotes successful Georgian women in STEM research. The section will contribute making STEM research more popular, encourage more women in their career advancement and increase the motivation of young female students.

JOINT FINAL CONFERENCE

INCLUSIVE RESEARCH AND INNOVATION ECOSYSTEMS

A SUSTAINABLE WAY FORWARD FOR GENDER EQUALITY

The **Université libre de Bruxelles (ULB)** consists of 13 Faculties, Schools and specialized Institutes covering all the disciplines. Founded in 1834, the ULB has a **long tradition of excellence in research with four scientific Nobel Prizes, one Fields Medal, three Wolf Prizes and two Marie Curie Excellence Awards**. The university also played a **pioneering role in the presence of women in Belgian universities**, welcoming the first three women university students, the first woman assistant, the first woman professor and the first woman rector in French speaking Belgium.

Within CALIPER, ULB developed Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) for its Faculty of Sciences and the Brussels School of Engineering. It also led the project efforts on design and development of the partners customised GEPs, the delivery of the internal engagement and change management strategy, as well as the tasks of intra-institutional communication in CALIPER.

PROJECT PARTNER

GREENLIGHT FOR POSITIVE ACTIONS IN HIGHER EDUCATION

Critical findings of a **'Legal feasibility study on affirmative actions' have been applied** to initiate change in the political landscape, to address women's under-representation. A **successful advocacy strategy was launched**, calling on Belgian decision-makers to support legislation for the implementation of positive action.

A **milestone in 2023 was achieved with the governmental approval of an 'implementing decree'** that enables positive action to be taken in the field of higher education in Wallonie-Bruxelles Federation.

INCREASED VISIBILITY FOR WOMEN IN STEM

Strong efforts have been made to shift the 'image' of gender & science and **enhance representation & visibility of women in STEM**. Initiatives include the establishment of a **Gender Target in STEM PhD juries**; actions to strengthen **Inclusive Communications** (i.e., trainings, dedicated gender equality webpages, language and imagery review of STEM webpages).

Initiatives to encourage a **next generation of female scientists** include a **Role Model video**; a **hands-on day of STEM exploration** with over 130 girls and volunteers; the Scientific **'Woman of the Week' campaign**; and the **International Day of Women & Girls in Science**, showcasing research excellence of female scientists and 'Sex/gender+ in STEM research'.

REINFORCED INSTITUTIONALISATION OF GENDER EQUALITY WORK

To guarantee sustained continuation and impact of the GEP, **gender equality work has been institutionalised**.

Two **permanent Gender+ Commissions in STEM Faculties have been created**, functioning as action-oriented Working Groups for gender equality initiatives. Importantly, **long-term change has been secured by the integration of STEM specific and transversal gender equality objectives of the GEP** into the central 'Gender & Diversity plan', ensuring key goals and learnings are embedded into institutional gender policy work.

GENDER BALANCE IN DECISION-MAKING STRENGTHENED FOR CENTRAL GOVERNING BODIES

A **gender balance norm for boards with advisory power has been achieved**. It stipulates a **33% gender representation standard** that needs to be applied to effective members, which is the critical threshold to achieve tangible impact in decision making processes. A **2-year Pilot for "Gender balance in central advisory bodies"** has launched, targeting 5 key boards: Research, Cultural, Teaching, Student social affairs and Discipline commission.

INCREASED AWARENESS TO COMBAT GENDER BIAS & SEXISM

Actions to raise awareness and tackle biases achieved the **publication of a Guide on Gender Sensitive Teaching promoting 8 practice tools for inclusive pedagogy**; a **workshop to enhance the gender dimension in the training of secondary school science teachers**; the integration of the **gender dimension and competences into the 'teaching profile'**; as well as **professional trainings to tackle discrimination & harassment**, promoting workplace diversity. Further, an institution wide **permanent poster campaign on Sexual harassment/violence services and protocols** across 3 campuses with over 150 frames and a dedicated webpage has been put in place.

CALIPER project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 873134

JOINT FINAL CONFERENCE

INCLUSIVE RESEARCH AND INNOVATION ECOSYSTEMS

A SUSTAINABLE WAY FORWARD FOR GENDER EQUALITY

The National Technical University of Athens (NTUA) is the most prestigious and most competitive academic institution for technical education in Greece. **NTUA participated to CALIPER project to design, develop and implement a Gender Equality Plan (GEP) for the School of Electrical and Computer Engineering (ECE).** The aim was to establish a well-adapted GEP, to support structural change through improved procedures, policies, and organisational structures. This way the partner managed to address gender imbalances and enhance in its academic, research and administrative activities

National Technical University of Athens
School of Electrical and Computer Engineering

PROJECT PARTNER

FIRST SCHOOL OF NATIONAL TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS TO ESTABLISH A GENDER EQUALITY PLAN

The School of Electrical and Computer Engineering (ECE) is the **first School of the NTUA to design and implement a Gender Equality Plan (GEP).**

The GEP has been successfully put into practice over the past two academic years (2021-2022, 2022 - 2023), and will continue being updated and applied in the foreseeable future.

GUIDE ON HARASSMENT, GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE, BIAS & SEXIST BEHAVIOUR ENDORSED

The ECE School is the first School of the NTUA to have established a **Guide on sexual harassment, gender violence, bias and sexist behaviour.** The Guide has been disseminated to all the School's personnel and is available at the ECE website.

INTEGRATION OF THE GENDER DIMENSION INTO TEACHING AND RESEARCH

The ECE School has **integrated gender topics into 3 undergraduate and 3 postgraduate courses,** as part of a continuing process. The School has also organized trainings on the use of inclusive language in teaching and on how to integrate the gender dimension in research.

CREATION OF GENDER EQUALITY OFFICE

The ECE School is the first School of the NTUA, to have established and operate a **Gender Equality Office.** Its responsibilities include, among others, the collection of data on gender equality and intersectionality, the dissemination and implementation of awareness raising events, and acting as a contact point for complaints on bias and gender-based violence.

COLLECTION OF GENDER EQUALITY DATA

The ECE School is the first School of the NTUA to have implemented an **annual data collection procedure.** The goal is to collect information on gender equality and intersectionality topics, and support decision-making.

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JOINT FINAL CONFERENCE

INCLUSIVE RESEARCH AND INNOVATION ECOSYSTEMS

A SUSTAINABLE WAY FORWARD FOR GENDER EQUALITY

The Institute for Research in Biomedicine (IRB Barcelona) is an independent, non-profit research institution engaged in **basic and applied biomedical science**. It was founded by the Government of Catalonia and the University of Barcelona in October 2005 and is member of the CERCA research centres. Since 2016 IRB has been working proactively towards the establishment of measures to improve Equality and Diversity at all levels of the organisation.

Being part of CALIPER project IRB has developed its dedicated comprehensive GEP and it has coordinated the task on overall GEPs refinement procedures by the CALIPER GEP implementing partners.

PROJECT PARTNER CALIPER

GENDER SENSITIVE RECRUITMENT PROCESS PUT IN ACTION

As part of the CALIPER efforts, the IRB reviewed, updated and disseminated **enhanced recruitment policies and guidelines**, assuring that the documentation has a **gender sensitive approach**

GENDER BALANCE IN THE IRB FACILITIES INCREASED

Thanks to the Group Leaders selection protocol, the number of **female Group Leaders has increased from 3 to 8** during the CALIPER lifespan. In addition, **Mentoring Programmes targeted for women GL** have been launched and envisioned to continue in a sustainable manner.

EQUALITY AND DIVERSITY TOPICS INTRODUCED INTO ONBOARDING PROCESS

IRB set up sessions that included explanation of the GEP, the actual CALIPER Project, ongoing actions, the **introduction of gender dimension into research**, working groups, and communication channels to address any questions or concerns related to equality and diversity topics.

NEW MEASURES TO TACKLE SEXUAL AND GENDER HARASSMENT

The organisation has **updated its internal protocol**, during the implementation phase of the CALIPER project. In addition, key internal stakeholders have participated in **advanced training activities** on these topics.

ENGAGEMENT AND AWARENESS ON EQUALITY AND DIVERSITY TOPICS PROLIFERATED

Several efforts have been made with the objective of **promoting and enhancing engagement in equality and diversity topics**. The initiatives planned within the CALIPER project, consisted of institutional equality and diversity videos, networking activities, creation of printed materials, roundtables, workshops and awareness sessions.

JOINT FINAL CONFERENCE

INCLUSIVE RESEARCH AND INNOVATION ECOSYSTEMS

A SUSTAINABLE WAY FORWARD FOR GENDER EQUALITY

Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development & Innovation Funding in Romania (UEFISCDI) is a **public entity of the Central Administration in Romania** under the authority of the Ministry of Education and Research. UEFISCDI was established in order to **promote quality and leadership for higher education, research, development and innovation.**

Committed to equal opportunities principles for all its employees and collaborators, UEFISCDI took part in CALIPER to create a **Gender Equality Plan (GEP) that provided a framework for the existing good practices** inside the organisation and outside its boundaries.

Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding

PROJECT PARTNER

IMPLEMENTATION OF A COMPREHENSIVE GENDER EQUALITY PLAN

Recognizing the pivotal role of gender equality in research excellence and societal impact, UEFISCDI took proactive measures to champion this cause.

Through the CALIPER project, we meticulously developed and rolled out a **comprehensive Gender Equality Plan**. The organisation aimed to create a more inclusive research environment, where **diverse perspectives are valued, and gender biases are actively addressed.**

CAPACITY BUILDING AND TRAINING INITIATIVES ORGANISED

Throughout CALIPER duration, UEFISCDI organised numerous **training sessions and workshops**, enhancing the understanding of gender issues among staff, researchers, and external stakeholders.

NATIONAL LEADERSHIP IN GENDER EQUALITY PROMOTION STRENGTHENED

UEFISCDI solidified its position as a trailblazer in advancing gender equality at the national level. We extended our expertise and resources to numerous universities and research institutes across Romania.

Our dedicated support **empowered these institutions to develop and implement their own Gender Equality Plans**, amplifying the ripple effect of our efforts.

PROMOTION OF GENDER-SENSITIVE RESEARCH METHODOLOGIES

UEFISCDI worked on the **integration of gender perspectives in research**, an action that has significantly reshaped our approach to funding. By updating the texts for funding calls, we ensured that gender considerations are front and center.

Moreover, we integrated the **gender dimension into research content as a mandatory requirement**, thus emphasising its importance.

COLLABORATION AND NETWORKING WITH EUROPEAN PARTNERS FORSTERED

UEFISCDI created strong collaborations with European research institutions, **sharing best practices**, challenges, and solutions related to gender equality in research.

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JOINT FINAL CONFERENCE

INCLUSIVE RESEARCH AND INNOVATION ECOSYSTEMS

A SUSTAINABLE WAY FORWARD FOR GENDER EQUALITY

Established in 2001, **Yasar University (YU)** has quickly become an ideal environment for research, personal development and learning consisting of 9 Faculties, 2 Graduate Schools, 1 Vocational School, 1 EU Research Centre, 1 Open and Distance Learning Centre, 1 Knowledge & Technology Transfer Office and 1 Continuing Education Centre. In CALIPER project, YU designed and implemented a Gender Equality Plan (GEP) to create a **ripple effect of change** within the university in terms of fostering gender equality in recruitment, working conditions and career development of women and elimination of any existing gender bias.

PROJECT PARTNER

ESTABLISHMENT OF THE GENDER EQUALITY BODY

The gender equality body "**Women & Family Studies Application and Research Center (YUKAM)**" has been established as a result of the work carried out within the framework of the CALIPER project. The Women & Family Studies Application and Research Center (Gender Equality Body) is now permanent structure of the University.

ESTABLISHMENT OF THE GENDER-BASED DISCRIMINATION, VIOLENCE AND SEXUAL HARASSMENT PREVENTION UNIT

In order to reduce gender-based discrimination and harassment and increase awareness about the subject a **Gender-Based Discrimination, Violence and Sexual Harassment Prevention Unit is established under YU Gender.** The Unit consists of two bodies: a) Coordinator, b) Commission: The commission made up of three academic members and one administrative member from the University.

GENDER-DISAGGREGATED DATA COLLECTION

An **official Gender-Disaggregated Data Collection procedure is established** to monitor the progress at institutional level. This will contribute to developing evidence-based policies for gender equality in the institution by monitoring the implementation of the policies on gender equality through gender disaggregated data collection at all levels.

INTEGRATION OF GENDER INTO INSTITUTIONAL STRATEGIC PLAN

Yasar University's **2020-2025 strategic plan includes objectives and indicators for research, education and awareness raising activities on gender equality.** The plan has been prepared with the participation of all relevant academic and administrative departments at the university on various subjects and sub-committees. **Gender Equality is included under two Strategic Objectives.**

EMPOWERMENT, MENTORING AND AWARENESS RAISING PROGRAM

An **online Empowerment, Mentoring and Empowerment Program is launched** to support career development of young female researchers. The program consists of **5 training videos** namely "Women and Career Development", "Gender Sensitive Teaching", "Gender Sensitive Communication", "Integration of Gender Dimension into Research", and "Gender Sensitive Human Resources Management". The trainings have become **internal part of the staff orientation program.**

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JOINT FINAL CONFERENCE

INCLUSIVE RESEARCH AND INNOVATION ECOSYSTEMS A SUSTAINABLE WAY FORWARD FOR GENDER EQUALITY

Since 1955 University of Salento (UNILE) has been promoting knowledge, skills and merit and has offered a large range of educational opportunities from law to science, economics to engineering, humanities to media studies. UNILE comprises 6 Faculties, several Hubs across 8 Departments providing services and information for students, as well as 33 Research Centres throughout the Salento area.

Within the CALIPER project UNILE has enhanced its Gender Equality Strategy with awareness and capability to improve **the enrolment and retention of women in science**, implement **work-life balance policies**, and **remove obstacles to women's career progression**

UNIVERSITÀ
DEL SALENTO

PROJECT PARTNER

INTEGRATION OF THE GENDER EQUALITY PLAN

The **Gender Equality Plan (GEP)** was designed and implemented with the approval of all governing bodies of UNILE. The plan is valid for the entire University and has a duration of three years. Some actions have been also included in the Strategic Plan of the University. This year, the **GEP was integrated into the UNILE's sustainability agenda**, which refers to the actions of the UN 2030 Agenda.

INTRODUCTION OF 'CAREER ALIAS'

UNILE CALIPER team has proposed the implementation of **'Career Alias' according to the university's own innovative model, that overcomes binarism**. The measure was approved by the Institution. What is more **the model has already been uptaken by other universities too**.

EMPOWERING FEMALE RESEARCHERS AND INTEGRATION OF GENDER DIMENSION

UNILE has activated **scholarships for female doctoral students and scholarships for female students in STEM courses with a minority of women enrolled**. Also, **three rounds of interdisciplinary and cross-sector seminars** have been completed. **Improved and gender-sensitive guidelines for the composition of scientific panels and round tables** for conferences and sponsorships have been approved by the university's governing bodies; while **an agreement on these issues was landed with the National Television Broadcaster (RAI)**.

TWO ROUNDS OF GENDER BUDGETING MEASURES

Throughout the CALIPER project lifecycle **two rounds of gender budgeting measures** were completed and put in action. The first round was introduced at the beginning of the project, while the second one was delivered during 2023.

ESTABLISHMENT OF AN OMBUDSPERSON AND OTHER SUPPORTING BODIES/RESOURCES

We have established and appointed an **Ombudsperson** for discriminatory behaviours for both male and female students and University staff. Also, **a medical center has opened at the UNILE campus, that also offers gynaecological counselings and psychological support**. Throughout the CALIPER duration, we have completed diverse cycles of **courses against gender-based violence**, as part of project's actions.

